

A GRAPH THEORETIC FORMULA FOR THE NUMBER OF PRIMES $\pi(n)$

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Abstract

Let $\text{PR}[n]$ be the graph whose vertices are $2, 3, \dots, n$ with vertex v adjacent to vertex w if and only if $\gcd(v, w) > 1$. It is shown that $\pi(n)$, the the number of primes no more than n , equals the Lovász number of this graph. This result suggests new avenues for graph-theoretic investigations of number-theoretic problems.

1. The Result

In *Written on the Wall* (or *WoW*), Fajtlowicz's notes on conjectures of his program GRAFFITI [2, 3], Fajtlowicz defined the graphs $\text{RP}[S]$ and $\text{PR}[S]$ whose vertices are a set S of integers [1]. For $\text{RP}[S]$, two distinct vertices are adjacent if and only if they are relatively prime; while in $\text{PR}[S]$, two distinct vertices are adjacent if and only if they have a non-trivial common factor (and are thus the complements of the $\text{RP}[S]$ graphs). Let $\text{PR}[n]$ be the graph where $S = \{2, 3, \dots, n\}$. *WoW* is indexed by conjecture numbers, often with useful commentary of its author and correspondents. These graphs are defined in *WoW* #434 (1988). Study of these graphs may yield new insights into number theoretic questions. Among other things *WoW* records Staton's proof of the interesting fact that *every graph is an induced subgraph of $\text{PR}[n]$, for some positive integer n* (*WoW* #446).

An independent set in a graph is a set of vertices which are pair-wise nonadjacent. The independence number $\alpha = \alpha(G)$ of a graph G is the cardinality of a maximum independent set. Fajtlowicz observed, and it is easy to see, that the primes are a

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maximum independent set in $\text{PR}[n]$ and thus the independence number of $\text{PR}[n]$ is the number of primes up to n , denoted $\pi(n)$. So $\alpha(\text{PR}[n]) = \pi(n)$. The Prime Number Theorem gives an asymptotic formula for $\pi(n)$ and the Riemann Hypothesis is equivalent to a conjecture about the error term in a formula for $\pi(n)$. Thus the study of the independence number of the $\text{PR}[n]$ graphs may yield new insights into $\pi(n)$. GRAFFITI is well-known for its conjectures for the independence number of a graph—many of which were proved. While following up on Fajtlowicz’s idea and also investigating the class of graphs where α equals Lovász’s theta function ϑ , we discovered the following new formula for $\pi(n)$.

Theorem 1.1. For every integer $n \geq 2$, $\pi(n) = \vartheta(\text{PR}[n])$.

This may be of interest for a few reasons: Lovász’s theta function is widely studied, has a number of equivalent definitions [4], is efficiently computable, and there is an efficient algorithm for recognizing graphs where the independence number α equals Lovász’s theta function ϑ .

An *orthonormal representation* of a graph G is an assignment of a unit vector \hat{x}_v to each vertex v in the vertex set $V(G)$ having the property that vectors assigned to non-adjacent vertices are orthogonal. Lovász’s theta function $\vartheta = \vartheta(G)$ of a graph G is defined to be the minimum over all feasible orthonormal representations $\{\hat{x}_v : v \in V(G)\}$ (or simply $\{\hat{x}_v\}$) and all unit vectors \hat{c} :

$$\vartheta = \min_{\hat{c}, \{\hat{x}_v\}} \max_{v \in V(G)} \frac{1}{(\hat{c} \cdot \hat{x}_v)^2}.$$

Proof. Let n be a positive integer. Since Lovász proved that for any graph G , $\vartheta(G) \geq \alpha(G)$ [5] and $\alpha(\text{PR}[n]) = \pi(n)$, it is enough to show that there is in fact a feasible orthonormal representation of $\text{PR}[n]$ and unit vector \hat{c} that realizes this lower bound; that is, such that:

$$\pi(n) = \min_{\hat{c}, \{\hat{x}_v\}} \max_{v \in V(G)} \frac{1}{(\hat{c} \cdot \hat{x}_v)^2}.$$

Suppose there are exactly k primes no more than n : p_1, p_2, \dots, p_k . For each vertex v with l_v distinct prime factors we define \hat{x}_v to be a k -component vector where the i^{th} component is 0 unless p_i is a factor of v in which case the i^{th} component is $\frac{1}{\sqrt{l_v}}$. It is easy to see that if v and w are relatively prime, and thus non-adjacent, then $\hat{x}_v \cdot \hat{x}_w = 0$. Then let \hat{c} be the vector whose components are all $\frac{1}{\sqrt{k}}$. Then $\max_{v \in V(G)} \frac{1}{(\hat{c} \cdot \hat{x}_v)^2} = \max_{v \in V(G)} \frac{1}{(l_v \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{k}} \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{l_v}})^2} = \max_{v \in V(G)} \frac{k}{l_v}$ occurs for a vertex w when $l_w = 1$, for instance when w is prime, and in this case equals k , the number of primes no more than n . \square

Since perfect graphs have the property that $\alpha = \vartheta$, it might be thought that the $\text{PR}[n]$ graphs are perfect. They are for $n < 35$. $\text{PR}[35]$ has an odd hole: $5 \cdot 7, 7 \cdot 3, 3 \cdot 11, 11 \cdot 2, 2 \cdot 5$.

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